

Corrosion inhibition of mild steel in aqueous solutions of alcohol

S. Sanyal

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Sahibganj College, Sahibganj-716 109, India

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Corrosion of mild steel in aqueous solutions of alcohol has been investigated. The rate of corrosion increases with increase in alcohol content upto 60% and then decreases. Organic salts like sodium benzoate and sodium mercaptobenzothiazole have been used as inhibitors. Both are anodic inhibitors as revealed from the polarization studies.

In continuation of our work on the use of sodium benzoate as inhibitor for mild steel in aqueous solutions^{1,2}, the corrosion behavior of mild steel (ms) in aqueous solutions of ethanol and performance of some soluble organic salts as inhibitors have been reported here.

Results and discussion

Properties of alcohol solutions :

Table 1 shows the viscosity (at 25°), as reported in the literature³ and the conductivity, experimentally determined (at 30°) of aqueous solutions of ethanol. It can be seen that the viscosity rises slowly with increase in alcohol content upto 60% by volume of alcohol, thereafter it falls upto 100%, whereas the conductivity of alcohol solutions is progressively reduced with higher alcohol content.

Table 1. Properties of aqueous solutions of ethanol

Alcohol content in aqueous solution % by vol.	Viscosity of aqueous solution of alcohol at 25° millipoise	Conductivity of aqueous alcohol solution at 30° $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
10	11.53	9.5×10^{-5}
20	15.39	8.6×10^{-5}
30	18.49	5.4×10^{-5}
40	19.91	4.8×10^{-5}
50	20.01	2.4×10^{-5}
60	20.07	2.4×10^{-5}
70	19.06	1.7×10^{-5}
80	17.44	1.6×10^{-5}
90	15.19	1.5×10^{-5}
100	12.70	0.8×10^{-5}

Effect of alcohol concentration :

Table 2 shows the weight-loss of metal during one month at 30° in aqueous solutions containing different concentrations of alcohol, along with final potential attained by ms. It can be seen that as the percentage of alcohol increases, the rate of corrosion increases upto 60% alcohol content.

Table 2. Weight-loss and potential values of mild steel at various concentrations of aqueous alcohol solutions for 30 days at 30°

Aqueous alcohol solutions % by vol.	Weight-loss mg dm^{-2}	Potential mV
0	318.16	-700
10	321.04	-600
20	326.38	-588
30	368.96	-546
40	481.87	-540
50	713.32	-492
60	768.16	-582
70	232.16	-498
80	163.56	-312
90	0.58	-208
100	0.58	-186

Thereafter there is sharp decrease in corrosion rates and corrosion is negligible in solutions of 90 and 100% of alcohol content. It is observed that in presence of higher alcohol content (more than 60%), the corrosion products are more adherent and thus protect further metal loss. The results also show that the potential values follow almost the same trend upto 60% alcohol content but are ennobled with further alcohol content. This observation is in conformity with that observed with lower corrosion rates in solutions with higher alcohol content and can be attributed to the reduced conductivity of the solutions^{4,5}.

Effects of temperature :

The effect of temperature on the corrosion of ms is shown in Table 3. The corrosion rate increases upto 60° which may be due to the desorption of the adsorbed molecules – inhibitive and/or aggressive – at higher temperature and thus exposing the fresh metal surface to further attack⁶ which results in intensification of the kinetics of electrochemical reaction⁴ and thus explains the higher corrosion rate at elevated temperature. The rate of corrosion then decreases

Table 3. Effect of temperature on mild steel in 60% alcohol solution (Duration, 7 days)

Temp. °C	Weight-loss mg dm ⁻²
30	46.31
40	63.56
60	78.92
80	54.04

at temperature higher than 60°. This may be due to some depletion of oxygen at higher temperature^{4,6}.

Effect of period of immersion :

It was observed that weight-loss of metal varies almost linearly with immersion period in 60% aqueous solution of ethanol. The corrosion product being non-adherent does not stifle the attack and hence the metal-loss varies linearly with time-period of immersion.

Corrosion inhibitors :

The two organic inhibitors, namely, sodium benzoate and sodium mercaptobenzothiazole (NaMBT) were tested in 60% alcohol solution and the results are shown in Table 4. It can be seen that there is appreciable metal-loss in 60% alcohol solution, having negative potentials. Cent percent protection

Table 4. Evaluation of (a) sodium benzoate and (b) NaMBT as corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in 60% (by vol.) aqueous ethanol solution at 30° for one month

Inhibitor conc. %		Weight-loss mg dm ⁻²		Inhibition %		Potential mV	
(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
0	0	768.16	768.16	-	-	-582	-582
0.03	0.01	136.32	114.14	32.25	85.14	-268	-264
0.06	0.04	92.06	82.16	88.01	89.30	-186	-234
0.075	0.06	40.71	20.46	94.70	97.33	-146	-212
0.1	0.08	18.94	4.62	77.53	99.39	-120	-188
0.25	0.1	1.36	Nil	99.36	100.00	-96	-120
0.5	-	Nil	-	100.00	-	-20	-

of metal can be achieved with both the inhibitors with ennoblement of the open-circuit potentials (OCP). The shift of OCP in the positive direction indicates the interference of these inhibitors with the anodic partial process⁷, blocking the anodic reaction sites of the metal electrodes⁸.

Polarization measurements :

Table 5 shows the cathodic and anodic potentials of polarization studies both in presence and absence of inhibitors of ms in 60% alcohol solution. It can be seen that there is no appreciable change in the cathodic polarization in presence of either sodium benzoate or NaMBT but the anodic polarization considerably increases in their presence.

Table 5. Polarization of mild steel showing potential values in presence and absence of inhibitors in 60% alcohol solution

log current density mA cm ⁻²	Potential (mV)					
	Without inhibitor		With 1% sod. benzoate		With 1% NaMBT	
	Cathode	Anode	Cathode	Anode	Cathode	Anode
0	-386	-380	240	-128	-360	-218
0.3	-400	-378	280	102	-390	-144
0.4	410	-364	-300	228	-410	-98
0.6	-420	-352	340	230	-468	92
1.0	-440	-348	-400	232	522	200
1.3	-462	-340	-440	230	-914	480
1.6	-800	-336	-502	230	-992	710
1.9	-1020	-330	-718	230	-1024	806
2.0	1040	-322	-910	230	-1042	848
2.3	-1066	-318	-994	230	-1062	880

Hence, the mechanism of corrosion inhibition is due to the blockage of the anodic sites – as also observed and supported by the shift of OCP in noble direction in presence of inhibitor.

Experimental

Metal specimens, their preparation, the methods of measurements of corrosion rates, potential and polarization studies were the same as reported earlier¹. The alcohol contents are expressed in percentage volume in aqueous solutions. Deionized water was used for making the alcohol solutions.

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